

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PROJECT-BASED LEARNING MODEL ON TEACHING-LEARNING OF ENGLISH

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to compare traditional methods of teaching with a new, technology-based, innovative model, known as Project-Based Learning (PBL). Comparisons are made both quantitatively and qualitatively. The study is experimental with a control group taught in a traditional way and an experimental group taught with the help of the PBL model, with an achievement test. The sample collected was purposive, and the sample size was 40. Students being homogeneous class with an inclusion of both boys and girls. Quantitatively, there was a significant difference in the measure of central tendencies between traditional teaching and the PBL model. Qualitative observations highlight that the PBL model had an impact on achievement test, but it was not limited to it; the PBL model inculcated a scientific attitude, curiosity, and it turned out to be quite enjoyable for students. The study does show a significant difference in achievement test quantitatively, and might be helpful in language classes with students with a diverse spectrum of intelligence. In future, the prospect of using this model for significant improvement of students might show significant improvement if the model is run for a longer period.

Keywords: *Project-Based Learning, Teaching Model, Traditional Teaching Method, Comparative study*

Introduction:

The idea of the research originates from the researcher's experience as both a student and a teacher, highlighting the need to incorporate 21st-century learning methods in language classes.

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As a teacher, the researcher observes that traditional teaching leads to a monotonous learning pattern, which impacts the long-term performance of students. To foster interest and build 21st-century skills among students, teachers need to adopt innovative models and technology while teaching. It is important for teachers to incorporate new and innovative models in the teaching–learning process of English. The PBL model offers a renewed approach to English language education. This student-centred approach allows students to move from exploration and understanding to actual application of learning. A comparative study between the traditional method of teaching and the PBL model, therefore, becomes a logical next step. Comparative studies are generally conducted using quantitative achievement tests; however, in the case of the PBL model, active student participation indicates that achievement tests alone are insufficient to assess important elements such as skill development, curiosity, and engagement. In a nutshell, a qualitative approach through classroom observation is also required, as it allows to analyse the short-term as well as long term impact of teaching models on the students.

NEP 2020 emphasises the need to move away from rote learning and build a more student-centred and active classroom experience for students. It stresses a more learner-centred pedagogy, collaboration, creativity and real-life application. This leads to the PBL Model being a strong recommendation as it aligns with the recommendations of NEP 2020.

Literary Study:

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is rooted in the idea of “learning by doing,” a philosophy promoted by American educator John Dewey. William Heard Kilpatrick later formalised it in the early 20th century as part of the progressive education movement. PBL emphasises real-world engagement, student autonomy, and active problem-solving. The PBL Model is based on the constructivist approach. The constructivist perspective focuses on students being the centre and believes that they construct their own knowledge through active participation and experiences. Learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas or concepts based upon their current and past knowledge (Bruner, J. S., 1961). According to Vygotsky, L. S. (1978), project-based learning is an innovative approach to learning that teaches a multitude of strategies critical for success in the twenty-first century.

Traditional vs PBL Model:

The traditional method of teaching highly relies on the teacher and is, hence, a teacher-centred approach. The teacher plays a primary role in delivering content information, explaining, and elaborating. This method often only results in building Listening skills and lacks the other basic 3 basic skills required in teaching English: Writing, Speaking, and Reading. On the contrary,

the project-based learning model is a constructivist approach that focuses on learning through meaningful projects and real-world problems. Students actively engage in inquiry and collaborate to build their knowledge. The teacher acts as a facilitator, guiding students throughout the learning process. The PBL ignites knowledge by building on skills like communication, collaboration and reflection.

The Project-Based Learning Model:

1. **Ignite and Initiate (Driving Question and Launch of the Project):** The learning starts with presenting a driving question related to real-life scenarios. The teacher presents the objectives and aims to connect the topic with the students' own experiences.
2. **Inquiry in Action (Conduct Inquiry):** The learners are at the forefront of this step as they conduct an inquiry by asking questions, researching and exploring resources. This stage encourages curiosity building and promotes independent work.
3. **Structuring the Learning Path (Design and Plan):** Students collaboratively participate in planning and designing a project. They assign roles, decide timelines, and determine ways to complete the project. This level leads to building teamwork and effective communication skills.
4. **Construct and Refine (Create and Critique):** Learners create project outputs such as models, presentations or performances. Peer feedback and teacher guidance are incorporated through the creation process to improve the quality of the project.
5. **Voice the Learning (Present the findings):** This is the presentation step where teams present their outcomes in front of their peers and teachers. This aids in building speaking skills, articulation and confidence.
6. **Reflection and Evaluation:** The last stage allows students to reflect on their entire process of learning, including skills acquired and challenges faced. The teacher evaluates both the process and the final product using rubrics, observations, and feedback. This step ensures meaningful learning and continuous improvement.

Statement of Aim:

To study the “Effectiveness of Project-Based Learning Model on Teaching-Learning of English” of Grade 9 students on the English literature topic – The Fun They Had.

Research Objectives:

- a. To examine the effectiveness of Project-Based Learning in teaching and learning of the English Subject.

- b. To compare the academic outcomes of the Project-Based Learning activity and the traditional teaching approach.
- c. To assess the factors influencing the impact of Project-Based Learning on learners.

Research Question:

- a. What is the impact of student outcomes of Project-Based Learning?
- b. How does PBL influence students' ability to use English in real-world, authentic contexts?
- c. How does project-based learning impact students' proficiency in English language skills?

Research Hypothesis and Null Hypothesis:

a. Research Hypothesis:

There will be a significant difference between the mean score of Project-Based Learning and the Controlled Group.

b. Null Hypothesis:

There will be no significant difference between the mean score of Project-Based Learning and the Controlled Group.

Operational Definition:

- **PBL Model:** This is a program developed by the researcher, which will be implemented on the experimental group of students, and their achievement test will be conducted.
- **Achievement Test:** This is an evaluation test designed to measure the skills and knowledge of the students.
- **The degree of understanding of learning outcomes** – Marks or scores achieved on the achievement test.

Research Methodology:

- **Type of research:** For the present study, Experimental research was used.
- **Variable Analysis:**
 - a. **Dependent variable:** Score on achievement test.
 - b. **Independent variable:** Teaching module (PBL, Traditional).
 - c. **Intervening variables list:**
 - 1. **Teacher-related:** Teaching style, teacher's ability, class control, instructions.

2. **Student-related:** Background, age, gender, IQ, previous achievements, privileges, inclination towards subject.
 3. **Class related:** Strength, seriousness.
 4. **School-related:** Board, curriculum, content.
 5. **Topic-related:** Previous knowledge, learning outcomes, and lesson plan according to Bloom.
 6. **Test related:** Test according to learning outcomes.
- **Sampling Techniques:** Purposive sampling technique.
 - **Sample Size:** 40
 - **Data Collection Tool:** Achievement test.
 - **Data Analysis Tool:**
 1. Mean
 2. Standard deviation
 3. t-test

Procedure of Research:

1. Preparation of content, activities, learning outcomes and lesson plan using Bloom's taxonomy.
2. Preparation of the achievement test according to content and learning outcomes.
3. Standardisation of both lesson plans and achievement tests.
4. Conducting lectures on both methods to one group each.
5. Conducting an achievement test on both groups.

Quantitative Analysis of the Data:

Data of research and representation:

Achievement test scores:

Using the measure of central tendency:

- a. Mean: significant
- b. Variance and standard deviation: significant
- c. T-test shown significant

Interventional Observations:

During Lecture Observations:

1. During the entire time of the course, the students showcased high levels of engagement.
2. Learners created unique and creative projects at the end.
3. Questioning based on activities was reciprocated between teachers and students.
4. Encouraging the students led to active participation.
5. Many students reflected on how they understood the actual meaning of researching through the course of learning.
6. During the project presentation, a student spontaneously improvised dialogue using appropriate tone and expressions, indicating natural language acquisition beyond textbook learning.
7. Students, towards the end of the program, recommended using the PBL model in more English classes.

During Test Observations:

1. Assessment was given with utmost seriousness by the students.
2. Students were able to effectively connect real-life, case-based assessment questions with the lesson content.

After Test Observation:

1. After the test, students interacted with the teacher extensively; discussions covered a wide range of ideas related to the lesson and beyond.
2. Students in the traditional teaching class expressed disappointment at not being part of the class where the PBL module was implemented, indicating increased interest in the PBL approach.
3. Students displayed a very friendly and open attitude toward the teacher, leading to comfortable and meaningful academic interactions.
4. Students asked reflective questions about the project and assessment, demonstrating a deeper understanding of the learning objectives.

Discussion and Conclusion:

1. The mean score of the experimental group is higher than that of the controlled group, indicating better academic performance among students taught through the PBL approach.
2. The calculated t-value is greater than the critical t-value at the 0.05 level of significance with 39 degrees of freedom, showing that the difference between the two groups is statistically significant.
3. This significant difference suggests that the Project-Based Learning model has a positive impact on students' achievement compared to the traditional teaching method.
4. Classroom observations further support the quantitative findings, as students in the PBL group demonstrated higher engagement, active participation, collaborative learning, and the ability to apply concepts to real-life situations.
5. The results align with constructivist learning principles, as PBL enabled students to construct knowledge actively rather than passively receiving information.

Scope:

1. The study will evaluate the impact of Project-Based Learning on improving secondary school students' English reading, writing, and speaking skills.
2. The research will evaluate the effectiveness of the PBL approach to improve the academic outcomes of the students.
3. The research will examine the factors influencing the impact of Project-Based Learning on learners.
4. The study will promote the incorporation of a project-based approach in language subjects.

Delimitations:

1. The research will be restricted to only the English Subject.
2. The research will be restricted to only Students of the Secondary Section.
3. The research will only consider the impact of project-based learning on English writing, reading, and speaking skills, excluding listening skills.
4. The effectiveness of project-based learning will be assessed through achievement test scores, along with student surveys and teacher interviews, excluding other forms of assessment.

Limitations:

1. The research will be limited by the small sample size, as it will only involve one Secondary school class.
2. The study will be constrained by the responses provided by the participants, as the data collected will rely on the accuracy, honesty, and the participants' feedback.

Possible Knowledge Contributions:

1. The findings could inform the design and development of English language curricula, highlighting how Project-Based Learning can be integrated into various aspects of language learning.
2. This research will help educators to better leverage the potential of PBL to enhance language proficiency, student motivation, and real-world communication skills.
3. The findings can help inform teacher education programs and professional development initiatives that prepare teachers to use Project-Based Learning more effectively in English subject classrooms.
4. The PBL approach can encourage the learners' active use of language in authentic, real-world contexts.
5. The research could show that students who engage in project-based activities improve not only their linguistic competence but also their critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills, all of which are vital for successful language acquisition.

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Lesson Plan:

Title: The Fun They Had (Chapter)

Grade: IX

Duration: 45Minutes (over the span of 2 weeks)

Objective: Students will be able to analyse and understand the theme of the chapter using the PBL Model and create a project related to the same.

Step 1: Ignite and Initiate (Driving Question and Launch of the Project):

- What are the evolutions in the education system?
- How can technology be implemented in education?

Step 2: Inquiry in Action (Conduct Inquiry):

- Teacher facilitates class discussion on themes: technology, individuality, and human interaction in education and asks guiding questions to encourage critical thinking and discussion: “What are the drawbacks of automated schooling? What should be preserved?”
- Students’ journal: How can we blend technology with traditional teaching methods? What are we doing today, and what more can we do?

Step 3: Structuring the Learning Path (Design and Plan):

- Teacher introduces the project: Redesigning Education for the Future
- The class is divided into small groups and assigned roles (e.g., Project Manager, Researcher, Designer, Presenter).

Step 4: Construct and Refine (Create and Critique):

- Teacher guides students through the research process, provides support with locating online articles, studies, and case studies and encourages students to focus on both the benefits and challenges of different educational models.
- Students collect data on the role of technology in education, classroom evolution, and student engagement and organise findings into a group report or visual representation.
- Based on research work, students in their groups start working on creating the project.
- Teacher and Peer feedback sessions are organized timely manner to enhance the project.

Step 5: Voice the Learning (Present the Findings):

- Class organizes a formal presentation to showcase their projects.
- Teacher evaluates presentations based on creativity, feasibility, technology integration, and overall design.

Step 6: Reflection and Evaluation:

- Teacher facilitates a reflection session to discuss the learning process, challenges, and successes.
- Encourage students to consider how their perspective on education has changed throughout the project.